

The Cage of Time

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ABSTRACT

"The Cage of Time" presents a distinctive fusion of physical and virtual elements, merging the tangible presence of a kinetic object-instrument with the immersive experience of VR (Virtual Reality) glasses. Through this hybrid approach, viewers are invited to explore the illusion of passing time in virtual space. As part of the ongoing artistic research project VRinMotion, "The Cage of Time" stands as a testament to the innovative possibilities of combining traditional kinetic, instrumental and animating mediums with immersive technology. Collaborating closely with the media and time-based artist Anna Vasof, the VRinMotion team pushes the boundaries of animation by bringing physical objects to life through stop-motion animation within the virtual realm. By blurring the boundaries between the physical and digital worlds, "The Cage of Time" not only offers a captivating experience but also prompts reflection on the nature of perception, reality, and the passage of time itself. Through this interactive installation, viewers are encouraged to contemplate the sound and the fluidity of existence and the interconnectedness of the tangible and the intangible.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Applied computing • Arts and humanities • Human computer interaction (HCI) • Interaction design

KEYWORDS

Expanded Animation, VR, Tangible Interfaces and New Forms of Experiences, Sound Art and Soundscapes, Playful Interactions and Experiences, Real Time 360 Video

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1 Introduction to ExperiMotion 3

Stop-motion is an animation technique that involves capturing photographs of objects or characters frame by frame. When these frames are displayed one by one in sequence, they create the illusion of movement. VRinMotion, an art-based research project, combines various stop motion techniques in VR setups. The project integrates artistic virtual experiences with philosophical, theoretical, and analytical concepts. Through four experimental workshops, the VRinMotion team collaborates with animation artists, collaborators, and students to expand artistic concepts of stop-motion and motion-capture in virtual and hybrid

environments. "The Cage of Time" is the culmination of ExperiMotion 3, a collaboration with media and time-based artist Anna Vasof. The objectives of ExperiMotion 3 encompassed exploring the relationship between real-world objects and their virtual counterparts, as well as manipulating the space-time continuum within VR to explore the notions of space and time.

2 Description of the Object and the Experience

"The Cage of Time" is a rotating object with a circular form, featuring 16 clock pointers mounted on the bars of the cage in succession, reminiscent of a pre-cinematic device. The rotation of the clock pointers "operates" on similar principles as a pre-cinematic animation, but here, the separation and succession of the frames occur digitally, resulting in a side effect: the fragmentation of the surrounding space. This affects the perception of continuity in VR media, multiplying the sense of spatial dislocation. This dislocation, combined with the impression of seemingly continuous time, calls our spatial existence into question.

The object itself is a kinetic sculpture in the form of a birdcage. It continuously rotates the bottom part and produces sound. The bottom part is made of a drum cymbal transformed into a clock panel with Latin numbers. When it rotates, it hits the cage bars that move slightly and produce a metallic sound. Static clock pointers are mounted on each of the cage bars. In the middle of the cage, a 360 camera is mounted and constantly records the space surrounding the cage and sends the footage to a computer; with the help of software, it fragments the space and creates the animated illusion of the rotation of the clock pointers. The audience can experience this time illusion by wearing VR glasses. In other words, when exhibition visitors wear these glasses, they are teleported inside the cage, experiencing the space fragmented and simultaneously seeing the rotation of the clock pointers. The illusion of passing time in this project is literal, as we use stop-motion to achieve it, and as a result, we fragment the continuous perception of space.

By closing one eye, the audience can interrupt the illusion of time and restore the feeling of continuous space and duration. A microphone from inside the cage also transfers the sound. With the help of software, the sound is also slightly manipulated, amplifying the claustrophobic and dizzy feeling of The Cage of Time.

3 The View From Inside the Cage

4 Reinventing the illusion of movement

Thomas Edison's kinetoscope (1894) can be seen as a precursor to current VR technologies [1]. This device created the illusion of movement for only one viewer at a time. Similarly, current VR technologies are also designed for individual experiences, although we don't describe them as displays of the illusion of movement but as VR because of their immersive nature. The immersive nature of these devices is both their strength and their curse, as not many people are in everyday contact with VR storytelling. The immersive effect often dominates the narrative of the images they display. In this sense, the current situation is somewhat reminiscent of the early cinema of attractions [2], when cinema was still searching for its dominant narrative forms and the artistic possibilities derived from them.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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REFERENCES

- [1] See Hendricks, Gordon. *The Kinetoscope: America's First Commercially Successful Motion Picture Exhibitor*. New York: Theodore Gaus' Sons, Inc., 1966.
- [2] See Tom Gunning, 1986. The Cinema of Attractions: Early Cinema, Its Spectator, and the Avant-Garde in: *Wide Angle*, No. 8, pp. 3-4.